

THE FUTURE OF THE COUNTRY-REFORMS IN EDUCATION OF UZBEKISTAN

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Musical art and culture

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Annotation: The article discusses the main directions of modern education, in connection with the introduction of new state educational standards and general education programs.

Key words: concept of the Republic of Uzbekistan, road map, state educational standards.

There is a big shift and progress in the republic in many sectors of activity and areas such as the economy, the political sphere, the legal sphere, as well as in the education system.

Innovations in the education system have made it possible and accessible to study in various educational institutions, in the country's universities. Places were allocated for full-time undergraduate education, evening department of universities, full-time education, correspondence, evening, as well as the opening of universities in foreign countries. "The main task was to train a specialist with a high level of professional culture and competence, adequate to the new requirements for the quality of school education. The effectiveness of solving this problem depends on solving a whole range of problems and tasks of higher pedagogical education related to the search for new approaches to building a teacher training system at a university and improving its content».¹

Reform is a change in the rules in the sphere of human life that does not affect the functional foundations, or a transformation introduced by legislative means. In particular, the process of transformation of the state, country, (territory, region) and society, initiated by the authorities for any need.

A great contribution to the development of public education was made by the Concept of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated April 29, 2019 No. UP-5712. Many points were agreed to improve not only the quality of education, but also a "Road Map" was attached - a step-by-step instruction for use, intended for the formation of New Uzbekistan.

The concept of "system of understanding" includes:

- 1) a set of views on something, phenomena; the main point of view, the guiding idea for their coverage.
- 2) a system of views on phenomena in the world, nature, society.
- 3) the leading idea, constructive principle in scientific, artistic, technical, political and other activities.
- 4) a system of ways to solve the problem.
- 5) a way of understanding, distinguishing and interpreting any phenomena, generating considerations and conclusions inherent only to him.

¹ Тригулова, А. Х. Предметная интеграция и ее значение в профессиональной подготовке будущего учителя музыки / А. Х. Тригулова. — Текст : непосредственный // Молодой ученый. — 2018. — № 12 (198). — С. 173-175.

And here are just a number of transfers that show distinctive positive indicators after the implementation of the Concept: training of personnel, retraining, strengthening the material and technical base, providing budgetary funds, modern methods and directions, putting five initiatives into practice, educating young people.

The acquisition of high-quality knowledge is carried out by the constant improvement of new knowledge, advanced training, the study and use of more and more new ways and methods of teaching in all areas of pedagogical activity. Circles are open in all subjects, reports on the work done are provided in writing, in the form of photos or presentations.

And all this continues to develop thanks to the Internet as well. Currently, there is a rapid flow of information through networks and in this vein it is necessary to keep up with the times. After all, the current young generation is very aware of this area and the task of teachers is to guide, teach to move in the right direction.

Ensuring the implementation of new state educational standards and general educational programs that meet the requirements of a modern innovative economy (PISA, TIMSS), the creation of network schools, the organization of uninterrupted supply of electricity, natural gas, drinking water - all this makes it possible to see results in the field of education.

Improvements are also noticeable in other areas: the development of sports, the creation of a youth parliament, the improvement of reading literacy, the construction of new houses, the creation of a women's committee, reforms in medicine and the legal sphere.

“If the body of society is the economy, then its soul and spirit is spirituality,” said Shavkat Mirziyoyev. “When deciding to build New Uzbekistan, we rely on two strong pillars. First, it is a strong economy based on market principles. The second is a strong spirituality based on the rich heritage of our ancestors and national values.”

The effective manager Shavkat Mirziyoyev, who won the fame of a reformer, introduced significant changes in education, the economy, and the personnel policy of the Republic due to a change in the relationship of power with the people - “Face to the People”. And Central Asia is one of the most important advanced regions of the world, which was considered the center of literacy.

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